

Imago Annual Summit Agenda

11 December 2025, The Spine, Liverpool

Time	Agenda	
09:30 – 10:30	<i>Registration and refreshments</i>	
10:30 – 12:00	Imago announcements: The sky's the limit	
12:00 – 13:30	<i>Networking lunch</i>	
Afternoon	Space 9	Spaces 7 and 8
13:30 – 13:40	Welcome: Richard Chiverrell, streamed	Welcome: Richard Chiverrell, Dean of School of Environmental Sciences, University of Liverpool
13:40 – 14:50	Hands-on training session on using Imago data products	Talks exploring the potential of satellite imagery for social research and policy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sondre Solstad, The Economist • Barbara Metzler, BBC Verify • Ben Vigreux, Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government
14:50 – 15:30	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>
15:30 – 16:30	Training session continues	Panel discussion Chair: Dani Arribas-Bel Panellists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donna Clarke, UK Health Security Agency • Barbara Metzler, BBC Verify • Rachel Franklin, Imago
16:30 – 16:45	What comes next? An overview of Imago's future, and how to stay in touch	